

THEORETICAL FOUNDATIONS OF THE INTERACTION BETWEEN FISCAL AND MONETARY POLICIES UNDER WAVES OF OPTIMISM AND PESSIMISM

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19435400>

Abstract. *In this article, we examine the views of foreign scholars on the interaction of fiscal and monetary policies under the assumption that agents have limited cognitive abilities. Based on the Keynesian model, the theoretical foundations of the studies on the possibility of agents' beliefs being subject to waves of optimism and pessimism under three alternative policy regimes are analyzed. The results of the studies show that there are new approaches to the existence of a strong relationship between output, inflation, government spending and public debt, regardless of the policy regime, with the beliefs of agents. That is, the stability of the system is characterized by constant fluctuations between optimism and pessimism. Along with these views, macroeconomic indicators of the monetary and fiscal strategies of the Republic of Uzbekistan are analyzed and scientific conclusions are drawn.*

Keywords: *fiscal policy, monetary policy, waves of optimism and pessimism, behavioral macroeconomics, fiscal surplus, monetary surplus, macroeconomic stability.*

Introduction

In a period when the joint role and importance of fiscal and monetary policies in stabilizing the economy is increasing, special attention is paid to developing the right policy mix in scientific research. It has also been emphasized that ensuring the mutual compatibility of these policies serves as the key to sustainable development in the future. Such studies include studying the interaction of fiscal and monetary policies through dynamic (Saltari et al., 2021) and static (Foresti, 2018) analyses. That is, these policies are emphasized as measures taken to eliminate the consequences of imperfectly competitive markets.

The importance of such analyses is also supported by recent empirical studies, which show that different dominance regimes exist in different countries. Fragetta and Kirsanova (2010) show that the UK and Sweden have a fiscal dominance regime, while in the US, government agencies interact without dominance, so their interactions are better described by a Nash equilibrium. Also, different structures of the interaction between fiscal and monetary policies have different effects on the outcomes of the policy mix and its institutional organization. In comparison with the Nash equilibrium, fiscal superiority can improve the outcomes of the policy mix if the central bank pursues a tight policy (Dixit and Lambertini, 2003a).

However, if the fiscal authorities do not sufficiently consider the future or aim for overproduction, the damage caused by the lack of leadership will be even greater (Kirsanova et al., 2005). In a Nash equilibrium, the two policies are implemented independently and are considered to be mutually incompatible. The theoretical approach in the article mainly studies the effects of different policy regimes under the assumption that agents follow simple heuristic rules in forming their expectations about the future. In this, we mainly assume that “agents form their expectations in a behavioral way,” as emphasized in the research of Peter Flaschel (Flaschel et al.,

2015; 2018). Flaschel et al. (2015) assume that agents can be fundamentalists or extrapolators in forming their expectations.

Third, it introduces an element of rationality by allowing agents to revise their forecasting rules. The applied learning mechanism generates endogenous waves of optimism and pessimism, as shown in Flaschel et al. (2018). At the same time, the theoretical basis of how the economy stabilizes under different combinations of fiscal and monetary policies in the presence of these destabilizing waves is analyzed (Chiarella et al., 2005; 2012, Choriev, 2024).

Literature review. The narrow scope of macroeconomic models for sustainable economic growth limits the ability to draw conclusions that are appropriate for the next stages of development. In this regard, it is not enough to draw conclusions using the RBS model and DSGE models to analyze the causes and effects of business cycle oscillations. As a modern economic approach, behavioral macroeconomics is giving rise to the use of new economic terms. This theory is based on the rational individual paradigm, introducing an element of rationality in such a way that individuals learn from their mistakes and switch to rules that give better results. This approach puts forward the idea of endogenously formed “animal spirits” - “spiritual moods”, that is, waves of optimism and pessimism, which drive the business cycle and are also affected by it, and uses this model to shed new light on a number of important issues (De Grauwe et al., 2019).

Also, much of the literature assumes that the government can subsidize factors of production in order to eliminate the inefficiencies caused by imperfect competition in the markets for goods and services and economic factors, and that this subsidy is financed by one-time taxes. This assumption is clearly unrealistic from a practical, that is, empirical, point of view. More importantly, such an approach weakens the potentially important role of monetary policy, namely the role of stabilizing the cost-effective aggregate fluctuations around the disturbed stationary equilibrium.

From the works of Keynes (1936) and Hicks (1939) to the studies of Kydland and Prescott (1982), macroeconomic theories have emphasized investment dynamics as an important channel for the transmission of aggregate shocks. Therefore, it is natural that investment spending plays an important role in the formation of optimal monetary policy. Indeed, it has been shown that the properties of the rational expectations equilibrium can change dramatically when the assumption of capital accumulation is added to the standard New Keynesian model under a given monetary regime (Dupor, 2001; Carlstrom and Fuerst, 2005).

Existing studies also deviate from real-world practice when it comes to the fiscal regime. It is common practice in this literature to completely ignore fiscal policy. Such models implicitly assume that the fiscal budget is always balanced by lump-sum taxes. In other words, fiscal policy is not always disruptive, and as Leeper (1991) argues, policies are characterized as “active” or “passive” depending on the extent to which they respond to shocks to the government debt. However, empirical studies such as Favero and Monacelli (2003) show that the description of postwar US fiscal policy as always passive is inconsistent with the facts. Moreover, it is well known from theory that the properties of the rational expectations equilibrium given monetary policy depend strongly on the nature of the fiscal policy. Thus, the optimal design of monetary policy should depend strongly on the fiscal regime in place. The implication is that the coherence of policies that are made independently of each other is expressed in terms of their coherence.

Analysis based on the optimal monetary policy model is usually limited to economies with stable long-term inflation. As a result, nominal rigidities do not have a real impact on economic activity and welfare in the long run. It follows that it is wrong to assume that assumptions about

zero long-term inflation or the existence of indexation have no impact on the optimal monetary policy form.

The existence of endogenous fluctuations of optimism and pessimism, or “animal spirits,” is important for monetary policy. Its consequences are analyzed by constructing a trade-off between output and inflation volatility. In standard DSGE models, this trade-off is always downward biased. This means that in such models, any attempt to reduce output volatility through the interest rate instrument comes at a cost, namely increased inflation volatility. In other words, if monetary authorities increase their desire to stabilize output volatility, they may succeed in reducing output volatility, but at the expense of increasing inflation volatility (Grauwe and Macchiarelli, 2015).

Methodology

This article analyzes the theoretical foundations of scientific works, summarizes them, and draws conclusions. These studies consider what changes will occur in the economy under a certain regime of policies, and the methods of induction and deduction are used in the research. Also, analyses are carried out based on the monetary and fiscal strategies of our Republic. Scientifically based conclusions are formed on these analyses.

Analysis and results

The model developed in Grauwe and Macchiarelli’s (2015) research is based on a micro-based, New Keynesian model with heterogeneous agents. The economy is described by aggregate demand, the Phillips curve, and the government debt equation. Forecasts of output, inflation, and government spending are formulated based on simple heuristics, i.e., inferences based on initial data. Thanks to the learning mechanism, the model generates endogenous waves of optimism and pessimism, i.e., animal spirits - the general mental state of agents, and fiscal beliefs - the trust and expectations in the government’s fiscal policy.

Monetary and fiscal policies operate through separate mandates and for separate purposes, and they interact in a non-corporate manner. This approach is based on the model used in De Grauwe and Kirsanova (2010). It is methodologically convenient to express the strategic interaction between fiscal and monetary authorities as a linear-quadratic optimization problem, since its solution is usually obtained in the form of two linear response functions. This approach, while simplifying the model, allows us to clearly show how monetary and fiscal instruments interact in different policy regimes. In general, if the main instrument of the Central Bank is the interest rate, the government implements fiscal policy by changing government spending. We also define the policy structures in three alternative interaction regimes, namely fiscal dominance (FD), monetary dominance (MD), and no dominance (ND), as follows:

Lack of dominance In the ND regime, the authorities make decisions simultaneously, without taking into account each other's reactions. This means that the fiscal policy instrument in the current period does not directly affect the monetary decisions, and the monetary policy instrument in the current period does not directly affect the fiscal policy. However, assuming that there is a smoothing of policy instruments, each policy rule is affected by the policy instrument of the other authority with a delay. This follows from the fact that if the authorities smooth their policy instruments, the policy variables of the past period become predetermined state variables.

In the fiscal dominance (FD) regime, the fiscal authority plays a leading role and can influence monetary policy. This means that the fiscal variable in the current period is included in the monetary policy rule. At the same time, the interest rate in the current period is not part of the

fiscal rule, since the government, due to its dominant position, determines government spending independently of the decisions of the central bank.

In the monetary dominance (MD) regime, the central bank plays a leading role and influences fiscal decisions. This means that the current period monetary policy variable affects fiscal decisions and is therefore part of the fiscal rule. At the same time, the current period fiscal policy variable does not affect monetary policy, since in this case the policy decisions are made by the central bank, not the government.

The fiscal rule follows a similar logic. In this case, the government responds to the variables of interest with a one-period lag, since it takes time to implement fiscal adjustments (Muscatelli and Tirelli, 2005). This reflects the fact that fiscal decisions are usually made at a lower frequency than monetary policy. Following the work of Fragetta and Kirsanova (2010), we define the parameters as follows. In the ND regime, the authorities act without taking into account each other's reactions. This means that the current period interest rate and government spending do not directly affect each other. However, since we assume that the authorities smooth their policy instruments, there are lagged variables in both equations. In the FD regime, the fiscal authorities can affect the current period interest rate.

Simultaneously, fiscal and monetary policies for 2026-2028 have been developed and approved for the sustainable development of the economy. In developing these strategies, an analysis of the current state of macroeconomic indicators and their forecasts were presented, and strategic directions were determined based on these indicators. When determining the strategic indicators of monetary policy for the coming years, it was assumed that domestic conditions would stabilize aggregate demand, moderate lending processes, increase wages proportional to labor productivity, return remittance growth to the medium-term trajectory, stable investment flows, and the fiscal deficit would not exceed 3 percent of GDP in the medium term.

According to the main monetary policy scenario, real GDP growth is projected at 5.5-6.5 percent in 2026, and 6-7 percent in 2027-2028. Even under the main macroeconomic development scenario and other shocks, monetary policy will implement measures aimed at reducing inflation to the 5 percent target level. Headline inflation is projected to reach 7 percent by the end of 2026, to decrease to the 5 percent target level in 2027 as a result of reduced external inflationary pressure and stabilization of inflation expectations, and to remain around this level from 2028. In order to ensure macroeconomic stability, it is aimed to implement measures aimed at increasing the country's sovereign credit rating and entering the ranks of upper-middle-income countries by increasing the volume of gross domestic product to \$200 billion and per capita income to \$5,000. It is also determined to diversify the public debt portfolio and manage currency risks in order to effectively manage public debt, as well as ensure that the ratio of public debt to GDP does not exceed 50 percent through the implementation of the public debt management strategy for 2026-2028.

Table 1

Table 1. Global macroeconomic indicators forecast for 2026-2028 under the base scenario

Indicators	2023	2024	2025	2026	2027	2028
World GDP growth, %	3,5	3,3	3,2	3,1	3,2	3,2
Global inflation, %	6,0	4,9	4,0	3,5	3,4	3,2
Gold price, average annual, uns/dollar	1 943	2 388	3 428	3 983	3 500	3 410

According to the Central Bank, the growth trends in the world economy are projected to be around 3.1-3.2 percent for 2026-2028. Also, the trends of a decrease in the global inflation rate from 4 percent to 3.2 percent require the adoption of certain significant monetary measures. Also, the forecasts of a downward trend in the price of gold in the world market, in turn, require taking into account macro-fiscal risks when developing fiscal strategies. It is also important to adhere to certain established fiscal rules.

There are also risks of an increase in the fiscal deficit as a result of the imbalance between budget expenditures and revenues. The formation of a fiscal deficit above 3 percent of GDP increases aggregate demand in the economy and creates additional inflationary pressure.

Figure 1. Forecasts of macroeconomic development indicators of Uzbekistan for 2026-2028 according to the base scenario

The GDP growth rate of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2026-2028 is projected to be around 6.1 percent, with GDP expected to increase from 1,954 trillion soums in 2026 to 2,520 trillion soums in 2028. The balance of public debt as of January 1, 2025 amounted to 40.2 billion US dollars, of which public external debt - 33.7 billion US dollars, public domestic debt - 6.5 billion US dollars, or 35 percent of GDP. It has been determined to implement measures aimed at maintaining this percentage share in the coming years. Under the influence of the formation of a fiscal deficit of around 5 percent of GDP, the inflation rate may be 0.7-0.9 percentage points higher than in the baseline scenario, and the GDP level may be 0.6-0.7 percentage points higher. In the event of a fiscal deficit higher than in the baseline scenario, there is a need to take measures to further tighten monetary policy. In this regard, the structural direction of fiscal policy is of great importance.

In particular, even if the fiscal deficit is relatively “normal”, that is, around 3 percent of GDP, if government spending is increased in conditions where the economy is showing high growth rates and there is a risk of “overheating”, such a policy will in fact take on a procyclical nature. This will increase existing inflationary pressures and reduce the effectiveness of monetary policy. In this case, it is important to conduct fiscal policy in a countercyclical manner, that is, based on budget rules tied to economic activity. During periods of high economic activity, it is important not to sharply increase spending compared to the plan and to maintain financial discipline.

Conclusion

In the implementation of key measures aimed at ensuring macroeconomic stability, measures will be taken to create conditions for the formation of general inflation at 6-7 percent in 2026 and core inflation at around 5-6 percent, and general inflation at around 5 percent from 2027, based on the widespread introduction of targeted inflation control mechanisms. In ensuring fiscal stability, fiscal rules will be strictly followed. In this regard, measures will be taken to reduce the consolidated budget deficit to 3 percent of GDP, improve tax administration, reduce the share of the shadow economy and increase the revenue base by eliminating ineffective tax incentives, ensure targeted and rational targeting of state spending, reduce ineffective budget loans and subsidies, and increase spending efficiency.

Effective management of public debt and contingent liabilities will be strictly implemented on the basis of target limit rules, whereby measures will be taken not to exceed the limit set for 2026 for newly signed external debt transactions to ensure that public debt remains at a safe level (50 percent of GDP), and to prevent an increase in fiscal risks on the state's contingent liabilities in the medium term, measures will be taken not to exceed the limit amounts for newly signed PPP projects in 2026. The success of fiscal and monetary policy strategies for 2026–2028 directly depends not only on official macroeconomic indicators and their instruments, but also on the expectations, confidence and behavior of economic agents. In particular, if consumers, entrepreneurs and investors form positive expectations about future inflation, economic growth, incomes and financial stability, this will accelerate the achievement of strategic goals through investment activity, consumption and an improvement in the business environment. On the contrary, increased uncertainty, weakening of fiscal discipline or worsening inflationary expectations can increase pessimistic sentiment and reduce the effectiveness of economic decisions. Therefore, in order to ensure macroeconomic stability, in addition to the coordination of fiscal and monetary policies, strengthening the confidence of economic agents, stable formation of expectations and creating a positive environment among market participants are also important strategic tasks.

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